

ISHLOV BERISH REJIMLARINI HISOBLASH VA TAYINLASH

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ANNOTATSIYA: Mashinasozlik ilmiy-texnikaviy progressning rivojlanishi, mehnat unumdorligining oshishi, iqtisodni jadallashgan rivojlanish yo’liga o’tkazishda eng muhim rolni o’ynaydi, ishlab chiqarish va sanoat tarmoqlarining ko’pgina turlari rivojlanishini aniqlab beruvchi sharoitlarni yaratadi. Texnologik jarayonlarni mukammallashtirish, avtomatlashtirilgan ishlab chiqarish va belgilab berilgan joylarda mexanizatsiyalashtirishni joriy qilish mashinasozlikning muhim vazifalaridir.

KALIT SO’ZLAR: Kesish rejimlari jadvali, Diametrni yo’nish, Ishchi yurishlar soni, Shpindelning aylanish chastotasi, Kesish tezligi, Bir daqiqali uzatib berish, Tokarlik, RDB ga ega bo’lgan tokarlik, Ariqchani yo’nish, Rezbani kesish.

АННОТАЦИЯ: Машиностроение играет важнейшую роль в развитии научно-технического прогресса, повышении производительности труда, переходе экономики на путь ускоренного развития, создает условия, определяющие развитие многих видов производства и отраслей промышленности. Совершенствование технологических процессов, автоматизация производства и внедрение механизации в отведенных местах являются важными задачами машиностроения.

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА: Таблица режимов резания, Ориентация диаметра, Количество рабочих ходов, Частота вращения шпинделя, Скорость резания, Подача за одну минуту, Точение, Точение с RDB, Ориентация паза, Обработка пазов.

ANNOTATION: Mechanical engineering plays the most important role in the development of scientific and technical progress, increase in labor productivity, transition of the economy to the path of accelerated development, and creates conditions that determine the development of many types of production and industrial sectors. Improvement of technological processes, automated production and introduction of mechanization in designated areas are important tasks of mechanical engineering.

KEY WORDS: Table of cutting modes, Diameter orientation, Number of working strokes, Spindle rotation frequency, Cutting speed, One minute feed, Turning, Turning with RDB, Groove orientation, Grooving.

NATIJALAR: hisob-kitobni jadvallarga kiritamiz.
 1-jadval. Kesish rejimlari jadvali.

operatsiya	O'tish	Ishchi yurishlar soni	Chuqurligi t, mm	Uzatib berish S, mm/o b	Shpindelning aylanish chastotasi n, ayl./daq.	Kesish tezligi V, m/daq.	Bir daqiqali uzatib berish m/daq.

010 Tokarlik	Yon qirrasini kesish	2	1,5	0,5	800	160	400
	Diametrni yo'nish	1	1	0,25	1200	245	300
015 RDB ga ega bo'lgan tokarlik	Yon qirrani kesish	2	1,5	0,5	800	160	400
	55,8-0,29 diametrini yo'nish	1	1	0,25	1200	245	300
	25+0,062 teshigini yo'nib kengaytirish	2	1,5	0,4	1400	245	560
	Ariqchani yo'nish Rezbani kesish		2,5	0,15	680	120	102
	21 teshigini parmalash	18	0,11	1,5	570	100	855
	25+0,062 teshigini yo'nib kengaytirish	12	10,5	0,21	1060	70	222
			1,5	0,35	1720	135	602
			0,5	0,1	2420	190	242
020 parmalash	6+0,3 teshigini parmalash	1	3	0,16	1590	30	254
025 Tokarlik	46-0,62 diametrini yo'nish	3	2,6	0,4	1750	135	690
030 RDB ga ega bo'lgan frezerlash	42-0,62 liskani frezerlash	1	4,0	0,8	515	40,5	329
	18,25+0,28 teshigini parmalash	1	9,12	0,33	593	34	195
	R _c 1/2 rezbasini kesish	1		1.814	89	5	161

2-jadval. Operatsiyalarga vaqt me'yori

Operatsiyanin g t/r	operatsiya	Vaqt me'yorlari, daq.				
		Σt_o	Σt_{yord}	$T_{tay.yak}$	T_{dona}	T_{donak}
010	tokarlik	0,32	1,3	2,5	2,62	2,71
015	RDB ga ega bo'lgan tokarlik	0,75	1,8	2	3,6	3,7
020	Parmalash	0,07	1,4	3,5	2,4	2,52
025	tokarlik	0,4	1,5	2,5	2,9	3,0

Xarajatlarning keltirilgan hisob-kitobini jadvalga kiritamiz. Qolgan operatsiyalar uchun keltirilgan xarajatlar hisoblab chiqilgan va ular ham 3-jadvalga kiritilgan.

3-jadval. Keltirilgan xarajatlar hisob-kitobi

Operatsiyalar	Dastgoh modeli	T _{sht} , daq.	S _Z , So'm	S _{EKSP} , So'm	K _S , So'm	K _{ZD} , So'm	S, So'm
010	16K20	2,62	119	100	2100	850	13.1
015	HAAS ST-20	3,6	119	100	11000	990	15.5
030	SMV-850	2.8	119	100	9500	600	18.5

MUHOKAMA: RDB ga ega bo'lgan tokarlik 010 operatsiyasi uchun hisoblashni amalga oshiramiz, 1 raqamli o'tishga 51-1,0 o'lchamda yon qirrani kesish.

Z_{6,7} = 2 mm qo'yimni 2 ta o'tishga bo'lamiz; t₁=1,3 mm, t₁=0,7 mm. [3] bo'yicha (S mm/ayl.) uzatib berishni tayinlaymiz:

S₁=0,5 mm/ob. va S₂=0,25mm/ayl.

Kesish tezligini quyidagi formula bo'yicha topamiz:

$$V = \frac{C_v}{T^m \cdot t^x \cdot S^y} \cdot K_v$$

bunda C_v -koeffitsient [3]; m,x,y – daraja ko'rsatkichi;

T – chidamlilikning o'rtacha ko'rsatkichi 30-60 daq.;

K_v – zagotovka materialiga ta'sirni hisobga oluvchi koeffitsientlar ko'paytmasining koeffitsienti.

K_{mv} = 1,25, yuzaning holati

K_{pv} = 0,8 asbob materiali.

K_{iv} = 1 Asbobning chidamlilik davrini: T=30 daq. deb qabul qilamiz.

K_v = K_{mv} * K_{pv} * K_{iv}

K_v = K_{mv} * K_{pv} * K_{iv} = 1,25 * 0,8 * 1 = 1;

Birinci o'tish uchun koeffitsientlar qiymatini: C_v = 340; x = 0,15;

y = 0,45; m = 0,2 qilib qabul qilamiz.

Ikkinchi o'tish uchun koeffitsientlar qiymatini quyidagicha qabul qilamiz:

C_v = 420; x = 0,15; y = 0,2; m = 0,2.

$$V_1 = \frac{C_v}{T^m \cdot t^x \cdot S^y} \cdot K_v = \frac{340}{60^{0,2} \cdot 0,5^{0,15} \cdot 0,35^{0,45}} \cdot 1 = 165,8 \frac{m}{min}$$

$$V_2 = \frac{C_v}{T^m \cdot t^x \cdot S^y} \cdot K_v = \frac{420}{60^{0,2} \cdot 0,5^{0,15} \cdot 0,35^{0,45}} \cdot 1 = 254 \frac{m}{min}$$

Shpindelning aylanish chastotasini quyidagi formula bilan hisoblab chiqamiz:

$$n = 1000 \cdot \frac{V}{(\pi \cdot d)}$$

$$n_1 = 1000 \cdot \frac{165,8}{3,14 \cdot 65} = 812,34 \frac{ayl}{min}$$

$$n_2 = 1000 \cdot \frac{254}{3,14 \cdot 65} = 1244,26 \frac{ayl}{min}$$

Aylanish chastotasini quyidagicha qabul qilamiz. n₁ = 800 $\frac{ayl}{min}$; n₂ = 1200 $\frac{ayl}{min}$; U holda kesishning amaldagi haqiqiy tezligi:

$$V_1 = \frac{\pi D n}{1000} = 3,14 \cdot 65 \cdot \frac{800}{1000} = 163,28 \frac{ayl}{min}$$

$$V_1 = 3,14 \cdot 65 \cdot \frac{1200}{1000} = 244,9 \frac{\text{ayl}}{\text{min}}$$

Bir daqiqalik uzatib berishni quyidagi formula

$$S_{\min} = S \cdot n$$

$$S_{\min 1} = 0,5 \cdot 800 = 400 \frac{\text{m}}{\text{min}}$$

$$S_{\min 2} = 0,25 \cdot 1200 = 300 \frac{\text{m}}{\text{min}}$$

Texnologik jarayon operatsiyalarini me'yorlashtirish .

Asosiy vaqtni hisoblash. Tokarlik operatsiyalari uchun asosiy vaqtni quyidagi formula bo'yicha aniqlaymiz:

$$t_0 = L \cdot \frac{i}{n \cdot S} \text{ min}$$

L – ishlov berishning hisobli uzunligi, mm;

i – ishchi yurishlar soni;

n – shpindelning aylanish chastotasi, ayl./daq.; S – uzatib berish, mm/ayl.

Ishlov berishning hisoblash uzunligi:

$$L = l + l_V + l_{SX} + l_{PD},$$

bunda l – mazkur o'tishda detalning o'lchami, mm;

l_V – asbobning o'yib o'rnatish kattaligi, mm;

l_{SX} – asbobning yumalab tushish kattaligi, mm;

l_{PD} – asbobning keltirish kattaligi, mm.

$l_{SX} = l_{PD} = 2$ mm ni qabul qilamiz.

Asbobni o'yib o'rnatish kattaligi quyidagi formula bo'yicha aniqlanadi:

$$l_B = \frac{t}{\text{tg}\varphi}$$

bunda t – kesish chuqurligi, mm;

φ – plandagi burchak

U holda asosiy vaqtni aniqlashning yakuniy formulasi quyidagicha bo'ladi:

$$t_0 = \left(1 + \frac{t}{\text{tg}\varphi} + l_{CX} + l_{PD}\right) \cdot \frac{i}{n \cdot S} \text{ min}$$

1. 010 Tokarlik operatsiyasi (yon qirrani xomaki kesish)

$$2. t_0 = \left(35 + \frac{1,5}{\text{tg}45^\circ} + 2 + 2\right) \cdot \frac{1}{800 \cdot 0,5} = 0,101 \text{ min}$$

Yon qirrani tozalab kesish

$$t_0 = \left(35 + \frac{1,5}{\text{tg}45^\circ} + 2 + 2\right) \cdot \frac{1}{1200 \cdot 0,25} = 0,13 \text{ min}$$

1. 010 Tokarlik operatsiyasi (62 diametrini yo'nish)

$$2. t_0 = \left(35 + \frac{1,5}{\text{tg}45^\circ} + 2\right) \cdot \frac{1}{800 \cdot 0,55} = 0,09 \text{ min}$$

Yordamchi vaqtni hisoblash

Operatsiya uchun yordamchi vaqt detalni o'rnatish va yechib olish, dastgohni boshqarish, detalni o'lchashga sarflangan vaqt to'planib, tuziladi.

Kichik seriyali ishlab chiqarish uchun barcha operatsiyalar uchun yordamchi va tayyorlash-yakuniy vaqt umum mashinasozlik me'yorlari bo'yicha aniqlanadi.

Texnik xizmat ko'rsatish, tanaffuslar va tashkiliy xizmat ko'rsatishlarning jami vaqti (α , β , γ) operativ vaqtdan foizlarda 8% ni tashkil qiladi.

Normativlar bo'yicha aniqlangan yordamchi, tayyorlash-yakuniy, shuningdek hisoblab chiqilgan dona va dona-kalkulyatsiya vaqti jadvalga jamlangan.

Yordamchi va asosiy vaqt har bir operatsiyaning barcha o'tishlari uchun jadvalda jamlangan.

Dona vaqtni quyidagi formula bo'yicha aniqlaymiz:

$$T_{dona} = (t_0 + t_{vsp}) \left(1 + \frac{\alpha + \beta + \gamma}{100}\right)$$

Dona-kalkulyatsiya vaqtini quyidagi formula bo'yicha aniqlaymiz:

$$T_{dona.k} = T_{dona} + \frac{T_{n.z}}{n}$$

T_{dona} – dona vaqt, daq.

t_0 – ishlov berishning asosiy vaqti, daq.

t_{yord} – yordamchi vaqt, daq

α , β , γ , - texnik xizmat ko'rsatish, tanaffuslar va tashkiliy xizmat ko'rsatish vaqti, operativ vaqtdan foizlarda

$T_{dona.k}$ – dona-kalkulyatsiya vaqti, daq.

$T_{tay.yak}$ – tayyorlash-yakuniy vaqt, daq.

Jami mehnat qamrovi. $T_{dona} = 14,32 \text{ min}$

$$T_{dona.k} = 14,83 \text{ min}$$

XULOSA: Texnologik jarayonni texnik-iqtisodiy asoslash va texnologik jarayonning ko'rsatkichlari.RDB ga ega bo'lgan 015 Tokarlik dastgohida tokarlik operatsiyasiga xarajatlar hisob-kitobini keltiramiz

$$Z = S + Y_{eN} (K_S + K_{ZD})$$

bunda S – texnologik tannarx, so'm;

$$S = \frac{(S_z + S_{eks}) t_{dona}}{60}$$

Y_{eN} – kapital mablag'larning ($Y_{eN}=0,5$) iqtisodiy samaraliligi koeffitsienti.

K_S , K_{ZD} – dastgoh va tegishli binoga sarflangan solishtirma kapital mablag'lar. Asosiy va qo'shimcha ish haqi hisob-kitobini quyidagi formula bo'yicha bajaramiz:

$$S_z = S_{Ch} \cdot K_D \cdot Z_N \cdot K_{OM} = 70 \cdot 1,7 \cdot 1 \cdot 1 = 119 \frac{\text{so'm}}{\text{soat}}$$

bunda S_{Ch} –ishchining soatbay tarif stavkasi, so'm/soat; (70 so'm/soat)

K_D – qo'shimcha ish haqi va ustamalarni hisobga olish koeffitsienti

$$K_D = 1,7$$

Z_N – naladchikning ish xaqini hisobga olish koeffitsienti $Z_N = 1,0$

K_{OM} – ko'p sonli xizmat ko'rsatishda ishchiga to'lanadigan ish xaqini hisobga olish koeffitsienti $K_{OM} = 1,0$

Ish joyidan foydalanish bo'yicha soatbay xarajatlar hisob-kitobini quyidagi formula bo'yicha bajaramiz $C_{eksp} = C_{chz} \cdot K_M = 100 \frac{\text{so'm}}{\text{soat}}$

Bunda S_{chz} – asosiy ish joyidagi soatbay xarajatlar, $C_{chz} = \frac{\text{so'm}}{\text{soat}}$

K_M – asosiy dastgohlar bajaradigan o‘xshash ishlarni mazkur dastgohda bajarishda xarajatlar necha marta ko‘proqligini ko‘rsatuvchi koeffitsient.

Dastgohga xarajat qilingan solishtirma kapital mablag‘larni quyidagi formula bo‘yicha hisoblaymiz:

$$K_C = \frac{s_s \cdot K_M \cdot C_p}{N} = \frac{350 \cdot 1 \cdot 1}{350} = 1000 \text{ so'm}$$

bunda s_s – dastgohni sotilish narxi, so‘m; (350 so‘m qabul qilamiz) K_M – transport va montaj xarajatlarini hisobga olish koeffitsienti ($K_M=1,1$);

S_P –operatsiya uchun dastgohlarning qabul qilingan soni ($S_P=1,0$);

N – detallarni yillik ishlab chiqarish hajmi.

Binoga sarflangan solishtirma kapital mablag‘larni quyidagi formula bo‘yicha hisoblab chiqamiz:

$$K_{ZD} = \frac{S_{PL} \cdot P_S \cdot C_P}{N} = \frac{30000 \cdot 10 \cdot 1}{350} = 850 \text{ so'm}$$

bunda S_{PL} – 1 m² ishlab chiqarish maydoni narxi; ($S_{PL}=30000$ so‘m), so‘m/m²;

P_S – o‘tishlarni hisobga olgan holda dastgoh egallaydigan maydon;

($P_S=10$ m²); S_P – operatsiya uchun dastgohlarning qabul qilingan soni ($S_P=1,0$).

Dastgoh egallagan maydonni quyidagi formula bo‘yicha aniqlaymiz:

$$P_S = f \cdot K_S = 20,1 \text{ m}^2$$

bunda $f=6,5$ –dastgohning plandagi maydoni, m²;

K_S –qo‘shimcha ishlab chiqarish maydonini hisobga olish koeffitsienti, ($K_S=3,2$)

$$C = (C_Z + C_{EKSP}) \frac{t_{dona}}{60} = (119 + 100) \cdot \frac{3,6}{60} = 13,1 \text{ so'm}$$

$$Z = S + E_H(K_C + K_{ZD}) = 3 + 0,5(11000 + 850) = 5928 \text{ so'm}$$

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